

A basic result of this study is, that life-systems serve to reasonable compensation for mutual well of his different positions by dyn. nonlin. nonequil. feedback linked scale-(in)variant (control) circuits

Theory of pán Kósmos (KT)

Positive: feedback (~ reinforcing loop) [- upward causation] [- bottom up]: e.g.: order/disorder ~ pre-adaptat. ~ harmonis. ~ balance ~ calm(ness) ~ equal. ~ immat. ~ naturisat. ~ vacuum ~ unconscious ~ pos. ~ rights ~ phylogen. variat. (~ biodiversity ~ redund.) [- mutability] ~ natural selection ~ epigenetics ~ postimprinting ~ regeneration (~ strengths) ~ prerehabilitat. (e.g.: gut flora) ~ bio: oikonomia (~ economics): para. ~ solidar. ~ selective ~ Trickle-up ~ inflat. ~ common welfare ~ deregulation ~ develop ~ natural ~ evolution ~ phylogenesis ~ folded ~ complem. ~ prophyl. ~ Yin-Yang ~ wu wei ~ TAI-CHE(I) ~ healthy (~ Orthomolecular Medical) ~ fasting (~ autophagy) ~ Yoga ~ Meditat. ~ Ayurveda ~ TCM ~ decontaminate ~ sustainable (~ lasting) [(UN)SDG] ~ subsistence ~ coop. ~ synergie ~ arête ~ eudaimonia ~ sympathy ~ synwell ~ sovereign ~ supreme(um) [- hypostasis ~ pure(ness)] (~ Plotin: hypostase: phýseis: nous/psyche = to hen)] ~ exergy ~ order (~ certainty) ~ symm. ~ necessity ~ I ~ H ~ security ~ saturated ~ to be ~ identity ~ origin(är) ~ altruistic ~ r-strategy (~ g) ~ golden spiral ~ tolerance ~ interior values ~ spiritual (~ mind): e.g.: warm empathy ~ relaxation ~ quiet ~ "memento mori" ~ constructive molecular bond ~ molecular orbital antibond ~ selfless (~ transparency) [-peace] ~ purposeless ~ consens ~ trust ~ binding ~ considerate ~ pos. stress ~ intensive quantities ~ internal friction (~ resistance) ~ frictionless ~ laminar ~ attractor; period. ~ global (~ Re < Re_k ~ order parameter) > 0,5 ~ stabil ~ regular ~ Re << Re_k = laminar ~ equal spatially temporally complex. ~ free: t ~ space ~ degrees of freedom (independ.) ~ self-org.(order)[regulat.] ~ negentropy ~ F (free E) ~ statistical pot. Ω ~ Ω_T(η) ~ V(ξ) ~ φ ~ a ~ ξ ~ events Ω (-Ω_T ~ φ ~ P ~ t) ~ quant. > qual. growth ~ resources extensive use ~ qual.-eidet. ~ profounder-supremes-signific. ~ dysmat. (~ demat.) ~ ethereal ~ myths ~ mystics ~ implicatio ~ deep sleep ~ silence ~ boredom ~ monotony ~ sensibility ~ impulsive ~ spontan. ~ intrins. ~ mirror neurons ~ soft: matter ~ ware ~ skills ~ capabil. ~ feelings 2. Order ~ creations ~ startups ~ innovations ~ inspirative ~ morphous ~ nomaly ~ regeneracy ~ perfect. ~ under-complex ~ becoming (~ Heraclitus) ~ change ~ do ~ re-ligio (self)knowledge ~ alernea ~ good ~ beauty ~ sharing ~ transpar. ~ liberate ~ equal. ~ solidar. ~ just (~ fair) ~ (self)regulat. ~ novelty ~ revolution ~ paradigm (~ injunction) shift ~ better ~ supremes ~ wider ~ profounder ~ multum, non multa ~ big is beautiful ~ generalization ~ quicker ~ more ~ apagoge ~ efflux (~ elevation ~ animist. ~ irrational ~ irreal) ~ surplus ~ acquire ~ supply ~ slow food ~ independent ~ liberare(lis) ~ eleútheros ~ positiv. ~ optim. ~ anarchy ~ idea ~ (trans) self-determin. ~ autonomy ~ underdeterm. ~ ex ante ~ well kósmos krátos ~ proairesis (Aristoteles) ~ pessim. ~ prevent. ~ joy ~ ananda ~ (self)love ~ curiosity ~ kindness ~ compassion ~ unconvent. ~ creative ~ safety ~ natural. (~ Aristot.) ~ skeptic ~ intuit. ~ genesis: natural ~ bio ~ culture ~ utopy ~ techn. ~ genuine ~ extrapolat. ~ anti-gravity ~ electro ~ filament ~ submergence (~ more is better) ~ less (under) development (e.g.: economy: countries) ~ legitim ~ apo-kalýptein ~ an-cratia ~ values: supremes-profounder-signif.-integr. [- e.g.: original ~ authent. ~ ident. ~ powerless ~ uncontrol ~ restructure Pi-Code]] ~ imagine ~ magic ~ erot. ~ UrFaust ~ approx. (~ compactificat.) ~ revers. ~ epigen. ~ trans (inter) [pre] personal ~ universal hypergoods ~ agenz ~ allopoiesis ~ accomodation (e.g. g.: plural., freedom, altruist.) ~ enlightenment i.w.s ~ kósmos ~ kosmosophrosyne ~ tranzendent ~ hypergenesis ~ supersynth. (e.g.: normal hierarchy ~ holon ~ holarchy) ~ homogeny ~ convergence ~ homology ~ correspondance ~ correlat. ~ post hoc ~ causa formalis ~ stochast. ~ deduct. ~ concomitance- and functional laws ~ descriptive ~ Kalama sutta ~ sermon on the mount ~ construct. behaviour maxim ~ attitudes (codex) ~ classes ~ conceit (~ arrogance) ~ fatalism ~ fanaticism ~ nihilism ~ induct. ~ happiness ~ mammon(ism) ~ less is more (~ small is beautiful) [- little but fine] ~ epagoge ~ reflux [- reductionismus ~ spiritualist.(ual.) ~ rational ~ real] > clans ~ strains ~ monetary ~ wrong ~ complicate ~ (neo)liberalism [- e.g.: (turbo)capitalist. (hyper)consume ~ religious select ~ Puritan. ~ Calvinist ~ protestant. ethics ~ intensiv. ~ success ~ power ~ precariat ~ speculat. ~ isolat.] ~ Neo-Feudalism ~ Tribut economy ~ rentiers ~ Fin.-Military-Industr.-Data-Pol.-Legal legitimated complex ~ A: Social-Eco-Liberal ~ conformism ~ inferiority complex ~ demand ~ subject behaviour ~ woves in sheepskin ~ secret org. ~ elitist ~ manipulat. ~ subtil ~ trivial ~ rudimentär ~ aftercare principle ~ Parkinson Law ~ Peter Principle ~ order mufty ~ decline (~ decadence) ~ totalitar. ~ tyranny ~ despotism ~ dictatorship ~ autocrat. ~ autoritaraty ~ dogmat. ~ ideology ~ fundamental. ~ overdeterm. ~ ex post ~ in deficit ~ abstine ~ democracy: local ~ direct ~ base ~ deliberative ~ consens (Hume) ~ affected (~ sufferer) ~ privileg. (elite) ~ conspiracy ~ synarchie ~ echo chamber ~ comfort zone ~ niche ~ conformation ~ filter bubble ~ suffering ~ luck ~ hate ~ greed ~ discontent ~ provocation ~ aggression ~ panourgia (Plato: euthydem) ~ passion(less) ~ euphemist. ~ vulgar ~ condition. ~ programming ~ legalist. (~ dogmat.) [- rights (jurist)] ~ illiquid. (~ Pi-Code) ~ postfact. democrat. ~ fake news ~ propaganda ~ discursive (~ reflect.) ~ regress ~ step backwards: natural ~ bio ~ culture ~ dystopy ~ interpolat. ~ waste ~ abundance ~ Junkies ~ legalis. criminal. ~ porno ~ wrong impetus ~ veloziferisch ~ Faust II ~ gravity ~ magnetism ~ voids ~ emergence (~ more is different)

prime (arché)-law (unit) SENSE (Liä Dsi) principle: (inter)actio ~ Hamiltons ~ H-Theorem ~ causa finalis ~ bifurcat. (~ singular.) pán best sover.-signif.-pure: kalá symbios(ūn) ~ cósmos ~ Ω-point ~ harmon. ~ synergy ~ Q ~ E_n ~ W_E ~ F_W ~ -S_W ~ d_x ~ P ~ I_W ~ pot. ~ rest (~ Parmenides) ~ rest pot. ~ realis. ~ zone = flow = metacognit. ~ golden age (spiral) ~ Dilmun ~ Dao = I-Ging ~ tiān 天 ~ value ~ māyā ~ mokshi ~ advaita ~ samsara = nirvana ~ ethos ~ art ~ epoché ~ ataraxia ~ sophrosyne ~ athaumasie ~ arête ~ eudaimonie ~ sympathy ~ agape ~ Delphi ~ euthymie ~ perfect. ~ Týlos ~ Paradise ~ Otopia ~ Tilmun (~ Arcadia) ~ securitas ~ torsion ~ weakest link in the chain ~ vortex (Re = Re_k) [- order parameter Φ = 0,5] ~ critical point (knots) in network (realm ~ constitut. ~ filament) ~ cluster ~ braids ~ moduln ~ attractors ~ (mani)fold ~ SDS

Neg.: feedback (~ balancing) [- downward causat.] [- top down]: e.g.: disorder/order ~ adaptation ~ neg. ~ duties ~ eschatology ~ dysbalance ~ mat. ~ rough society ~ ordinary matter ~ seeming ~ conscious ~ cultural selection ~ ontogenet. variabil. ~ genome ~ genet. ~ preimprinting ~ degeneration (~ weaknesses) ~ rehabilitat. need ~ ↓purificat. ~ convent. ~ Trickle-down ~ deflat. ~ rezess.(depress.) ~ reregul. ~ postgrowth ~ less develop ~ artificial ~ involution ~ ontogenesis ~ unfolded ~ therapy ~ Yin-Yang ~ addiction (drugs) [pollution] ~ ill ~ poison ~ anergy (~ ineff ~ win) ~ chaos (~ risk) ~ dyssymm. ~ random ~ I ~ H ~ insecurity (~ fear) ~ unsaturated ~ essential needs ~ show ~ typis. ~ competition ~ K-strategy (~ r) ~ logarithm. spiral ~ exterior ~ personality disorders [e.g.: egocentric ~ cold ~ interdepend. ~ synth. ~ integr. (Sorokin) ~ good(ness) ~ narcissistic (~ corrupt) ~ bipolar ~ compulsive (~ obsessive)] ~ evolvement ~ vital. (~ Platon) [- bios] ~ pollut. principle ~ destructive molecular bond ~ molecular orbital bond ~ evolution ~ vision ~ syntopy ~ real utopy ~ war (~ violence ~ conflict ~ mistrust ~ crisis ~ coincid.) ~ aim ~ cosmogenesis(gony) ~ cosmic network ~ pressure ~ mania: ego ~ techno ~ positiv. ~ ruthless (~ membrane) ~ fulguration [- pattern (structure) format. ~ bifurcat. (cascade)] ~ extensive quantities ~ external friction (~ resistance) ~ dysergie ~ ±G ~ EM ~ emergence ~ fulgurat. ~ agens [- Reynolds number Re > Re_k ~ instabil ~ irregular ~ order parameter < 0,5 ~ Re >> Re_k = chaotics turbulent ~ emerging (e.g.: economy: markets) (e.g.: Re_k, krit. ≈ 1 = degree of turbulence)] ~ attractor: chaot. ~ local ~ unequal spatially temporally complex. ~ unfree: space ~ t ~ binding (~ constraints) [- interaction forces] ~ depend. ~ (apo)kálýpsis ~ ±collaps (~ Pi-Code) ~ Faust I ~ entropy (~ J/K) ~ kT ~ η ~ ξ ~ t ~ -Ω_T ~ φ ~ Φ ~ P ~ t ~ (~ approach ~ scaling) ~ interpersonal ~ resources intensive use ~ quant.>qual. degrowth ~ trans behaviour (relation) ~ synrevers. ~ quant.-mechan. ~ superficially expand ~ syngenet. ~ s-e (~ bio) dyn. ~ conditioning ~ sex ~ matter (~ down ward: reimmaterial.) ~ explicatio ~ enlightenment ies (permanent) ~ kósmogenesis [- e.g.: degrowth ~ resorption (resorbent)] ~ transimmanent ~ syngenesis ~ hypersynthesis ~ dream sleep ~ insomnia ~ restless(ness) ~ ana(logy) ~ parallel. ~ coevolunt. ~ coincid. ~ causa efficiens ~ insens. ~ unfeel. ~ cool(ness) ~ confrontat. ~ extrins. ~ d.-chaos ~ uncondit. + statist. Laws (~ cond. prob.) ~ Bible ~ Veden ~ Koran ~ epen ~ hard: matter ~ ware ~ skills ~ functionings ~ feelings 1. Order ~ structure ~ destruction (~ disruption) ~ establishment ~ exovations ~ imitation ~ act. ~ amorphous ~ anomaly ~ dysgeneracy ~ imperf. ~ over-complex ~ habit ~ let ~ compensation action: religion ~ satisfaction ~ ignorance ~ error ~ misbelief (~ false fetish ~ golden calf: e.g.: technic ~ market ~ ego ~ hedonist. ~ property ~ addictions ~ liberal ~ growth) ~ evil ~ lie ~ deception ~ hybrid ~ depress. ~ doping ~ tumour (early stages) [- cancer] ~ unfreedom (~ constraints) [- dependences] ~ ugly ~ mad(ness) ~ bondage ~ disparity ~ unsolidarity ~ injustice ~ business as usual ~ grocer soul ~ estrangement ~ control ~ paradigm (~ injunction) ~ duty ~ respons. ~ liable ~ status quo ~ reform ~ deal ~ worse ~ less ~ bourgeoisie ~ paradigm (~ injunction) ~ arrogant ~ fanaticism ~ nihilism ~ induct. ~ happiness ~ mammon(ism)

P-N ~ ±: Feedback control (~ circular causat.) [- causality]: Values ~ Behaviour: e.g.: order/chaos ~ intermittency ~ exaptation ~ superpos. ~ regulations ~ probab. ~ dyn. balance ~ transmat. (~ re)vital. ~ aether ~ (self) underconscious ~ vital: (trans)mutation ~ diversibil. ~ suitable ~ convenient ~ selection ~ proteome ~ inter: genet. ~ imprinting ~ climate (~ behaviour) ~ habitat. (~ e.g.: g-b-barrier) ~ economy: cycle ~ stagflat. ~ ±regulation ~ non equilibr. systems ~ alive ~ devolution ~ ±folding ~ (self)healing ~ I-Ging (~ Tao: wei-ji) [- (Liä) Dschuang Dsi] ~ sick ~ ±sufficient ~ ±better ~ ±t ~ T: term: short ~ Φ ~ long ~ ±disorder [- ambi (polyvalent)] ~ asymm. ~ probab. ~ ±I ~ H ~ ±security ~ states ~ process ~ essence ~ strategies: r/K ~ g/r (Piketty) ~ Thoreau ~ i-e values ~ profit rate ~ spiral: Fibonacci ~ Gemüt [e.g.: emot. (passion) ego ~ control ~ affects] ~ atomic orbital interaction ~ resilience (~ doubt ~ critic) ~ rest (erōē) ~ meaning ~ stress (compensate.) ~ compromise ~ consider. ~ ±unfree: space ~ t (~ immat.) ~ complexity (~ laws) ~ flow (~ vortex) [- braids ~ knots ~ spirals ~ attr.: point ~ g-l] ~ xýntopy (~ ±E) ~ partition function Z ~ order param.: fct. η = functional F [η(r)T] ~ f(±Ω_T) ~ sheafs ~ brans ~ Ω ~ α(t) ~ ζ(t) ~ univers. φ(±Ω_T) ~ (P) ~ f(Ω) ~ H-functional ~ utility ~ Güte growth ~ phil. of nature: ontolog.: eidet.-teleolog. ~ significat. ~ (im)material ~ complicatio ~ agent ~ feelings ~ conservation ~ brain network ~ pattern (~ structure) [formation] ~ behav. ~ moderate ~ ±control ~ ±trans(volution) ~ character ~ (self)realizat. ~ symm. breaking (~ branching) ~ rebellion ~ morphogenesis ~ ±anomalía ~ ±perfect. ~ ±: truth ~ real. ~ wisdom ~ kindness ~ moderate ~ less or more ~ anagoge ~ synflux ~ ±real ~ ±rat. [cybernet. feedback (control) cycles] ~ substitute (act) ~ gain ~ interact. circles ~ interdepend. ~ synth. ~ integr. (Sorokin) ~ good(ness) ~ cosmo-indiv. ~ interest ~ sukha ~ benefaction ~ evolution ~ vision ~ syntopy ~ real utopy ~ cosmogenesis(gony) ~ cosmic network (~ membrane) ~ fulguration [- pattern (structure) format. ~ bifurcat. (cascade)] ~ ±G ~ EM ~ emergence ~ fulgurat. ~ agens ~ emerging (e.g.: economy: markets) ~ (apo)kálýpsis ~ ±collaps (~ Pi-Code) ~ Faust I (~ approach ~ scaling) ~ interpersonal ~ trans behaviour (relation) ~ synrevers. ~ syngenet. ~ s-e (~ bio) dyn. ~ conditioning ~ sex ~ chron. stress (~ burn out) [- neurasthenia] ~ enlightenm ies (permanent) ~ kósmogenesis ~ transimmanent ~ syngenesis ~ hypersynthesis ~ ana(logy) ~ parallel. ~ coevolunt. ~ coincid. ~ causa efficiens ~ insens. ~ unfeel. ~ cool(ness) ~ confrontat. ~ extrins. ~ d.-chaos ~ uncondit. + statist. Laws (~ cond. prob.) ~ Bible ~ Veden ~ Koran ~ epen ~ destruction (~ disruption) ~ establishment ~ exovations ~ imitation ~ act. ~ amorphous ~ anomaly ~ dysgeneracy ~ imperf. ~ over-complex ~ habit ~ let ~ compensation action: religion ~ satisfaction ~ ignorance ~ error ~ misbelief (~ false fetish ~ golden calf: e.g.: technic ~ market ~ ego ~ hedonist. ~ property ~ addictions ~ liberal ~ growth) ~ evil ~ lie ~ deception ~ hybrid ~ depress. ~ doping ~ tumour (early stages) [- cancer] ~ unfreedom (~ constraints) [- dependences] ~ ugly ~ mad(ness) ~ bondage ~ disparity ~ unsolidarity ~ injustice ~ business as usual ~ grocer soul ~ estrangement ~ control ~ paradigm (~ injunction) ~ duty ~ respons. ~ liable ~ status quo ~ reform ~ deal ~ worse ~ less ~ bourgeoisie ~ paradigm (~ injunction) ~ arrogant ~ fanaticism ~ nihilism ~ induct. ~ happiness ~ mammon(ism)

~ more (over) developed (e.g.: economy: countries) ~ illegitim (~ il)legal ~ iniquity ~ excesses ~ intransparence ~ euphemist. ~ etikette ~ neurot. ~ melancholy ~ insults ~ secular ~ kalýptein (~ caste) kratia: e.g.: Oligo ~ Fisko ~ Mono ~ Phobo ~ Mafia ~ patronage ~ Organism. Crime ~ oligarchy ~ lower drives (e.g.: instinct, power abuse, control constraint) ~ differ. ~ iterat. (~ renormizat.) ~ irrevers ~ genet. ~ mind disease (misery) [cold] ~ conceal ~ subtle alienation (~ patronizing) ~ incapacitate ~ heteron. ~ subversive ~ charismat. ~ hyperagenz (~ soloipsismus) ~ anything goes ~ ego hypergoods (e.g.: liberty) ~ enlighten. i.n.s ~ cosmos ~ cosmophysics ~ immanent ~ degenesis ~ dyssynthesis ~ (self)destroy ~ pathology ~ hierarchy ~ heterarchy ~ heterogen (inhomogen) ~ divergence ~ illusion ~ lack of impulse (self)control ~ self-enrichment ~ affective disordered superparasit (system) ~ spiral: misallocation ~ injustice ~ (social) exclusion ~ disincentives ~ intentional (system. [calculate] misery (impoivement) ~ exploitation ~ disparticipat. ~ privileg. ~ project ~ causal. ~ propter hoc ~ causa materialis ~ determin. ~ induct. ~ causal and teleologic explanations ~ normative ~ Torah (ten commandments) ~ deadly sins ~ destruct. maxim